

Design of a Digital Imaging and Machining System Programme for Human Bone Implants

Eriyeti Murena, Samson Mhlanga, Nicholas Taisepi, and Charles Mbohwa

Abstract----Computer Aided Design and Computer Aided Manufacturing (CAD/CAM) is now used in the medical field as well. This paper outlines the design process and the final software package for a human bone implants. A Computer Tomography (CT) scan was used to scan the knee bone and the scanned pictures were sent to Digital Imaging Communication in Medicine (DICOM) viewer. The DICOM images with Digital Communication in Medicine (DCM) format were converted to Joint Photographic Expert Group (JPEG) format. Subsequently a PDF to Drawing (DWG) converter was used to convert the PDF file to DWG file format compatible with Mastercam. The final stage of the system involved generation of the NC (Numerical Control) code for the knee bone drawing and machining of the bone implant by the CNC machine. Oracle database express system has been used to design platform.

Keywords—Computer Aided Design (CAD), Digital Imaging Communication in Medicine (DICOM), Computer Tomography (CT), Computer Numerical Control (CNC) machines, Human bone Implant, Imaging.

I. INTRODUCTION

DESIGNING of implants inculcates in itself knowledge and understanding of a number of fields and collaboration between specialists in medicine and manufacturing to come up with an efficient solution. This includes data collection from patients, development of implant dimensions based on measured data, biomechanics studies for function and motions (since a natural joint's bones are coupled by ligaments), prototyping to verify the functional aspects and material selection (biocompatible, high strength to weight ratio).

Once a simple design of implant is ready, implantability issues (design for ease of implantation) are verified by virtual implantation accompanied with surgeons' feedback. The main objective of this paper is to detail the steps for designing knee bone implant using the image capturing and processing system, a program for machining the implant on a CNC machine, the network system for implant design processing as a platform for further development of systems.

Eriyeti Murena is with the National University of Science and Technology (phone: +263 9282842; fax: +263 9286803; e-mail: eriyeti@gmail.com).

Samson Mhlanga is with Industrial and Manufacturing Engineering Department, NUST, Zimbabwe but currently a PhD candidate at Faculty of Engineering and Built Environment, University of Johannesburg, South Africa (e-mail: smhlanga126@gmail.com).

Nicholas Tayisepi is with the Mechanical Engineering Sciences Department, Faculty of Engineering and Built Environment, University of Johannesburg, South Africa (e-mail: matandanicholas@gmail.com).

Charles Mbohwa is with the Quality and Operations Department, University of Johannesburg, South Africa, (e-mail: cmbohwa@uj.ac.za).

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

A. The Image Capturing System

Two basic digital imaging systems are, Computed Radiography (CR) and Direct Digital Radiography (DDR) [1]. Computed Tomography (CT) scanning uses special x-ray equipment to generate multiple views of the inside of the body. These multiple x-ray views are reconstructed into cross-sectional images of the body using computer systems. Radiologists use CT scan imagery to more easily diagnose medical problems such as some cancers, cardiovascular disease, trauma, and musculoskeletal disorders. The computer algorithms used to reconstruct CT scanner images are very computationally intensive, which forces medical equipment manufacturers to strike a balance between image resolution, image generation time, and system cost when designing a new CT scanner. Higher image resolution provides more visual diagnostic details to the radiologist, but it takes longer to generate the images [2].

B. Image Evaluation and Image Processing

The first obvious results of any CT examination are the axial cross-sectional images. Since these images are already available in digital form on a storage medium, they can be processed immediately by the processor. The evaluations of geometrical parameters such as distance, area, angle and volume as well as density measurements are part of clinical routine today. The tissue density is determined using the CT number averaged over a defined evaluation area, the so-called Region Of Interest (ROI). Geometrical parameters can be defined more accurately than in conventional radiography, since the problems of superimposition and distortion do not exist in CT [3].

Computer Aided Design, (CAD), system uses computers to assist in designing and sketching work. CAD is very helpful in some areas such as the use of appropriate scale, object manipulation, display and printing. Currently, there are various types of CAD software such as AutoCAD, Solidworks, CATIA, and MasterCAM. In this study, CAD will be used to design the related implant. The primary imaging modalities that are made use of in different application include, CT/MRI, optical microscopy, micro CT, Using data derived from these images, computer models of human joints for stress analysis, dynamic force analysis and simulation; design of implants and scaffolds [4].

C. The CT Scanner

Also known as a CAT (Computer Axial Tomography) scanner employs tomography is a medical imaging method.. Tomography is the process of generating a two-dimensional

image of a slice or section through a 3-dimensional object (a tomogram). The CT scanner uses digital geometry processing to generate a 3-dimensional (3-D) image of the inside of an object. The 3-D image is made after many 2-dimensional (2-D) X-ray images are taken around a single axis of rotation - in other words, many pictures of the same area are taken from many angles and then placed together to produce a 3-D image [5].

A CT scanner emits a series of narrow beams through the human body as it moves through an arc, unlike an X-ray machine which sends just one radiation beam. The final picture is far more detailed than an X-ray one. Inside the CT scanner there is an X-ray detector which can see hundreds of different levels of density. It can see tissues inside a solid organ. This data is transmitted to a computer, which builds up a 3-D cross-sectional picture of the part of the body and displays it on the screen. Sometimes a contrast dye is used because it shows up much more clearly on the screen. The accuracy and speed of CT scans may be improved with the application of spiral CT. The X-ray beam takes a spiral path during the scanning - it gathers continuous data with no gaps between images [6].

D. DICOM Viewer

DICOM Viewer provides the following basic tools for the manipulation and measurement of images:

- Fluid zooming and panning
- Brightness and contrast adjustments, negative mode
- Preset window settings for Computed Tomography (lung, bone, etc.)
- Ability to rotate (90, 180 degrees) or flip (horizontal and vertical) images
- Segment length

III. THE KNEE BONE IMPLANT DESIGN METHODOLOGY

A. The Layered Bone Concept

A biomimetic based design approach where the mechanical properties of bone in terms of its Young's modulus have been retrieved from the CT images using a QCT based approach. A layer based CAD model is then developed with each layer associated with a definite property. The layers of the CAD model were then associated to specific unit cells with matching mechanical properties to generate a biomimetic bone structure. Fig. 1 shows the layered bone model and its associated properties.

The model is divided into layers and the measurements are changed from pixels to millimetres where one pixel is equal to 0.174mm. The measurements are then transferred to AutoCAD.

Fig.1 The layered model of a bone structure

B. The JPEG To PDF Concept

This concept involves transferring the pictures from the CT scan to DICOM viewer and then pictures are converted to JPEG to PDF and lastly to AutoCAD (dwg). Fig. 2 shows the steps of the process.

Fig. 2 The conversion process

C. Modelling Of The Implant

In order for a customized cervical implant to be feasible, a strong working relationship between Medicine and engineering must exist, where Medical Image Processing (MIP), Computer Aided Design (CAD) and CNC manufacturing is involved in an integrated process chain to minimise time and cost.

D. CT Image Fusion

Overlay a colour-mapped PET image onto a CT scan to obtain anatomical references for regions with increased Fluorodeoxyglucose (FDG) uptake values. Use the ellipse tool to measure maximum, minimum and average values of Standardized Uptake Value (SUVbw) calculated using body weight) in a specified area. Image fusion can also be applied to other imaging modalities, such as Magnetic Resonance, e.g. DWI images can be fused with T1 or T2-weighted scans. Exporting the images go to menu tool bar and the click export image

Fig. 3 Exporting the image

A VB systems was developed to aid in converting the JPEG image to PDF format as shown in Fig. 3.

E. Converting JPEG To PDF

Realising that AutoCAD software did not have a format that accepted JPEG but PDF thus the need to develop the conversion. The Figure 4 shows the process of Converting from PDF to AutoCAD drawing format DWG or DXF

Fig. 4 Any PDF to DWG converter

When converting PDF to AutoCAD drawing the following should done:

Click on Add PDF Files button to add the files to be converted and the click Add a Folder to button to add some files Fig. 4 shows the layout of the converter.

- The output file type is DWG
- The output file version AutoCAD 2010/2011/2012
- Then the output folder is C:\Users\MURENA\Desktop
- Click the option button and the following will screen will shown
 - Pages to convert: All pages
 - Click on convert scanned PDF (Image PDF) to DWG/DXF
 - Vector tracing : outline
- Output options
 - Scale factor is 10
 - Overwrite existing DWG/DXF files click on replace original then click ok

IV. COMPUTER AIDED DESIGN

CAD, known as computer-aided design and drafting (CADD), is the use of computer technology for the process of design and design-documentation. CAD software is a type of computer program that replaces tedious manual drafting with an automated process. This software can helps explore design ideas, visualize concepts through animations and photorealistic renderings, and simulate how a design will perform in the real world. AutoCAD software was the first and most widely used CAD software. The following CAD software will be used for the design and programming of the model for the project

- AutoCAD
- Mastercam

A. CAD Software Program Features

CAD software has different features depending on which design process is being used. One version provides features for two-dimensional (2D) vector-based graphics, and the other version is for three-dimensional (3D) modelling of solid surfaces. Three-dimensional CAD programs enable designers to apply multiple light sources, to rotate object in three dimensions and enables the designs to be rendered from any angle more about 3D CAD software

B. AutoCAD

AutoCAD is a computer-aided drafting software program used for creating blueprints buildings, bridges and computer chips. AutoCAD is used mainly by drafters, although engineers, surveyors and architects may need to use the software from time to time. The Fig. 5 below shows the knee bone joint in 2D in AutoCAD. The drawing shows the features which were produced during conversion from PDF to Dwg.

Fig. 5 Knee joint 2D drawing

C. Mastercam

Mastercam is a powerful software able to both design 3-D models and prepare files for machining. When importing the model to Mastercam the Drawing should be first saved as a lower version of AutoCAD. Since the Mastercam version used is 2005 version the drawing can be saved as AutoCAD 2004 so that it can open on Mastercam.

D. Importing the model to Mastercam

1. Open Mastercam X
2. Using the prompts at the top left of the screen, proceed through these clicks:
File/Converters/<Click your file's converter type>/Read File

3. Fig. 6 shows the procedures to open the model. Browse to find your file and open it
4. A dialogue box will appear, accept defaults and click OK and your model should appear on screen.
5. If a warning asks if you would like to delete the current tool, click, No. Your model should now appear.
6. Position your model in the window by using the fit, zoom, and rotation buttons.

E. Cleaning The Model

This step is usually optional if a good model or surface has been created in the original program. Sometimes an import may have some odd, residual lines that are not part of your designer that are not supposed to be read by the machine. on the delete tool and selecting each line for deletion.

1. The "Screen-Repaint" button will refresh the image on the screen

2. Use the string of clicks to delete all non-surfaces:

Main Menu/Delete/All/Lines...Arcs...Splines...Points..., etc.

When done, click Main Menu to exit from the delete function. Click the Screen-Repaint button to refresh the image on the screen.

Fig. 6 The position model

The Fig. 6 shows the positioned model which has been zoomed and rotated to fit the working space

Choosing a machine type definition

The machine type definition allows the user to run various Mastercam product types such as Mill, lathe and router. The Fig. 7 shows the machine types menu it enables the user to choose the machine type definition.

Fig. 7 Machine type menu

V. MILLING TOOLPATH TYPES

Mastercam mill has several types of tool path that can be created on wireframe, surface and solid models. It contains a

variety of path but for this design a contour toolpath will used. This toolpath type is appropriate for both roughing and finishing applications. Contour toolpaths remove material along a path defined by chains or curves. To begin creating a contour toolpath, choose contour tool path from the toolpath menu. The chaining toolbar will appear on screen and then select the window chaining. The chain is selected on screen by selecting the part of the mould to be machined then click ok. To begin creating a contour path choose the tool parameter and the contour parameters. Under the "Tool Parameters" tab, right click in the open box and choose "Get tool from Library". Select the appropriate tool by double clicking on it. Use the "filter" (button at top left of dialogue box) to help reduce the number of options shown at any one time. Once the tool has been selected, its icon should appear in the tool parameter box then right click on the tool to see/confirm its specifications.

A. Post Processing Tool Path Operations

All the operations in the mastercam part file are listed in the toolpath manager. Before posting operations, the machine setting for each group. The settings include the name of post processor and the name of the NC file that will be written This will open the Post Processing dialogue box. The AXYZ postprocessor should be used. If it is not shown in the dialogue box, choose "change post" and choose it from the list (it will be the first one on the list). Click on save NCI, as well as save NC.

When prompted, save the file to a desired location. DO NOT SAVE FILES ON THE CAD/CAM Computers. They will be deleted regularly. Be sure the file is labelled as an NC file type. Saving the file will cause your G-Code to be written. Once it is written it may be opened the file using any text editor, but this may not be necessary.

A. Verifying Operations

The verifying function is used to create a 3D simulation of machining selected operations. The model created by this function represents the surface finish.

B. Running The Verification

To begin verification, select one or more operations in the toolpath manager list, then click the tool path verifying button. Use the control buttons to locate at the top of the verify dialogue box to start, pause, rewind etc the verify simulation. Use the dialogue to

- To select the tool display mode: turbo ,simulate tool and holder
- Select display parameters affecting movement speed and quality of simulation.
- Select stop/pause conditions

Fig. 8 The machining process

C. The Network System For Implant Design

The network system to be design will enable the automatic conversion of the CT scan images from the CT scanner to AutoCAD. This system has been designed using the oracle design system. The network system is shown in Fig. 9 and it contains the following tabs

- View CT scan
- Convert to DWG
- Exit

Fig. 9 The CT scan diagnosis system

To view the CT scan click on the A button the DICOM viewer software will appear on screen. This will enable the all the CT scan that have been produced from the CT scanner to viewed on the DICOM viewer software screen. In order to view the scans then browse for the folder which contains the images and the images will automatically show up on the screen. After converting to PDF the dialogue box will appear on the screen the click 'yes'. Then follow the process.

The PDF to DWG converter dialogue box will appear on screen, select the following

- Unit of measure in mm
- Select the output path C:\Users\MURENA\Desktop
- The single PDF file name PDF_Output.PDF
- The image position should be centred.
- Click add files and after adding the file then click save

PDF

The Fig. 10 shows the process of Converting from PDF to AutoCAD drawing format DWG or DXF

Fig. 10 The PDF to DWG converter

After completing the full conversion of CT Scan to AutoCAD click 'ok' to view the results.

VI. CONCLUSION

This process is the cheapest and effective way of designing knee bone implants compared to other processes which maybe expensive do not give academic platform for further development. The Design of a Digital Imaging and Machining System Programme for Human Bone Implants which is an approach to ease the challenges faced by the community in the design and manufacture of implants this programme will eliminate the system of importing implants from other countries. The developed programme is able to achieve our objective of Design of a Digital Imaging and Machining System Programme for Human Bone Implants. Using the programme it is possible to design a knee bone implant for which the measurements are individual based for each patient. The programme links several medical and engineering softwares in order to provide CNC machining program which will enable the knee bone to be machined. Further developments of this programme to cover a broader spectrum are envisaged. The developments should take into account the use of medical software which is able to scan patient and produce the actual measurements of the implant as per patient. The use of medical softwares which are able to transfer the scan pictures to Engineering softwares in 3D.

REFERENCES

- [1] Widmer W R , Acquisition Hardware For Digital Imaging, Vol. 49, No. 1, Supp. 1, 2008, Pp S2–S8
- [2] Siemens AG, 2011 Computed Tomography Its History and Technology, Medical Solutions Computed Tomography, Siemensstr. 1 , D-91301 Forchheim, Germany.
- [3] Starly B., Fang Z., Sun W, Shokoufandeh A. and. Regli, W, 2005, Three-Dimensional Reconstruction for Medical-CAD Modeling, Department of Mechanical Engineering and Mechanics, Department of Computer Science, Drexel University, Computer-Aided Design & Applications, Vol. 2, Nos. 1-4, pp 431-438.
- [4] Shapi' A I, Sulaiman R, Hasan M.K and. Kassim A.Y.M, (2011) An Automated Size Recognition Technique For Acetabular Implant In Total Hip Replacement ,International Journal of Computer Science & Information Technology (IJCISIT), Vol 3, No 2, 2011 DOI : 10.5121/ijcsit.2011.3218.236.
- [5] n.p. (2009, June 10). "What Is a CT Scan? What Is a CAT Scan?." Medical News Today.
- [6] <http://www.medicalnewstoday.com/articles/153201.php>.
- [7] <http://usa.autodesk.com/adsk/servlet/item?siteID=123112&id=17690382>
- [8] www.radiantviewer.com/dicom-viewer-manual/image_fusion_pet-ct.htm